

EVALUATING THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF CHAMOMILE TEA LEAVES EXTRACT IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INSULIN RESISTANCE AND OXIDATIVE STRESS IN FEMALE OBESE SUBJECTS

Kiran Aslam^{*1}, Mehak Noor², Adan Riaz³, Maham Saeed⁴, Muzammil Arshed⁵,
Hamna Wahab⁶, Urwah Andleeb⁷, Aleena Anwar⁸, Laiba Shahid⁹, Syeda Maha Tauheed¹⁰,
Syeda Safoora Tauheed¹¹, Masooma Ali¹²

^{*1,6}Department of Nutritional Sciences, Govt. Graduate College of Home Economics, Faisalabad

^{2,3,4,8,9,10,11}Department of Nutrition and Dietetics, The University of Faisalabad

^{3,5,7,12}Department of Nutritional Sciences, Govt. College for Women University Faisalabad

^{*1}kiranaslam@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17462495>

Keywords

chamomile tea, phytochemical, polyphenols, oxidant status, antioxidant capacity, insulin resistance, obese subjects

Article History

Received: 08 September 2025

Accepted: 15 October 2025

Published: 28 October 2025

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Corresponding Author: *
Kiran Aslam

Abstract

Insulin resistance is a common metabolic problem in obese people, defined by the body's inability to respond to insulin adequately. Excess adipose tissue, especially visceral fat, leads to chronic inflammation and the release of cytokines which disrupt insulin signaling. Furthermore, increasing free fatty acid levels and changed adipokine profiles (such as decreased adiponectin and increased leptin) impair glucose metabolism. These modifications promote hyperinsulinemia, which raises the development of non-communicable diseases. Herbal teas like cinnamon and ginger also show promise in supporting metabolic health and managing insulin resistance. Chamomile tea may help improve insulin sensitivity and reduce blood glucose levels due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. For this purpose the firstly chamomile tea extract were prepared and after preparation the phytochemical profile was observed of chamomile tea extracts were check to evaluate its antioxidant capacity. After that the efficacious capacity of chamomile tea was checked in obese females on the basis of specific criteria. Overweigh 60 obese females were selected randomly and divided further into 3 groups In which G₀ was considered as control group and G₁ and G₂ were considered as treatment group .Control group was given no treatment while treatment group G₁ & G₂ was given 300 mg and 600 mg of chamomile tea extract for the periods of 45 days. Serum Blood parameters were drawn and studies before imitation and after the trial. Insulin resistance in term of Hba1c along with serum insulin was measured and compared on 0th day and 45th day. Results were calculated by applying mean and standard deviation by using 2 way ANOVA test. The study demonstrated that, chamomile tea may serve as a gentle, natural aid in managing insulin resistance by improving glycemic control and reducing inflammation, complementing broader lifestyle and medical interventions.

INTRODUCTION

Obesity has been closely related to type 2 diabetes for centuries, and the primary reason for this is obesity's capacity to cause insulin resistance. Insulin resistance is a critical aspect of the etiology of type 2 diabetes and has been linked to a variety of additional pathophysiologic sequelae, including hypertension, hyperlipidaemia, atherosclerosis (also known as the metabolic syndrome or syndrome X, and polycystic ovarian disease. (1) Insulin is a peptide secreted by the pancreas that regulates blood glucose levels. Insulin resistance is the major cause of both diabetes and other metabolic disorders. Insulin resistance is also prevalent in the obese and overweight populations. Insulin resistance is caused by visceral and subcutaneous fat deposition, which affects biomarkers on the cell membrane that are important for insulin action. Insulin resistance causes high blood glucose levels, which lead to a variety of metabolic disorders. (2).The term "insulin resistance" usually refers to that insulin is being resistant effects on glucose metabolism, and storage. Insulin resistance in overweight and type 2 diabetes is characterized by diminished glucose transport on the basis of insulin-stimulation and metabolism in adipocytes and skeletal muscle, as well as inadequate reduction of hepatic glucose output. (3)Obesity accelerates the etiology of type 2 diabetes by raising insulin resistance. The lack of understanding of insulin resistance has limited T2DM treatment options. However, multiple investigations described the relationship between mitochondrial dysfunction, inflammation, hyperinsulinemia, and lipotoxicity and insulin resistance. (4).Oxidative stress, genetic background, ageing, hypoxia, and lipodystrophy are all implicated in the etiology of T2DM by inducing insulin resistance. Nonetheless, none of these principles has resulted in the development of effective Type 2 diabetes mellitus medicines. The cause could be a lack of agreement on cross-linked mechanisms of insulin resistance in Type 2 diabetes mellitus (5) Obesity is defined as severe adipose tissue enlargement caused by

increased dietary intake and insufficient energy expenditure. Diabetes mellitus, on the other hand, is a complex chronic condition characterized by elevated blood glucose levels or hyperglycemia caused by defects in insulin secretion, action, or both. Obesity may developed severely low-grade systemic and local inflammation that contributes to the establishment of insulin resistance-linked diabetes mellitus.(6) Chamomile, an annual plant of the Asteraceae or Compositae family, originated in Southern and Eastern Europe. This herbaceous plant has a branched erect stem, long and thin leaves, and paniculated flower heads composed of white ray florets and yellow disc florets. Chamomile flowers have a wide range of medicinal and pharmacological qualities; hence the plant has been listed in the pharmacopoeias of 26 nations. (7).Numerous in vitro and in vivo investigations have established the wound healing, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial capabilities of chamomile formulations. Chamomile has been shown to have beneficial effects on digestion and nervous system function. (8)The primary phenolic chemicals found in chamomile flowers include flavonoids and glycosides, coumarins, and phenolic acids. Chamomile's antioxidant capabilities are mostly related to its phenolic compounds, specifically flavonoids and their glycosides. (9). Although chamomile tea has been shown to improve insulin sensitivity through its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, there are still significant research gaps. The majority of earlier studies was limited to animal models or small human trials and lacked compelling clinical evidence. There is no standardized dosage or production method, and the long-term effects and mechanisms of action are not well studied. These gaps highlight the need for larger, well-controlled human trials to determine the efficacy of chamomile tea as a natural therapy for insulin resistance

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Raw Material

Chamomile tea leaves used in this study were procured from local garden. Upon acquisition, the chamomile tea leaves were visually inspected and confirmed to be free from any visible debris, dust, or foreign particles, as per standard herbal processing protocols (10).

Preparation of chamomile tea extract from methanol

Methanol extraction of bioactive compounds from chamomile tea leaves is a prominent method in phytochemical and pharmacological research due to its strong polarity and efficacy in solubilizing phenolic and flavonoid molecules. The dried chamomile tea leaves are then ground into a fine powder using a mechanical grinder to maximize surface area and improve solvent penetration. A certain amount of powdered sample, typically 10 to 20 gm, is then soaked in methanol at a 1:10 to 1:20 (w/v) ratio in a clean, amber-colored conical flask. The mixture is macerated on an orbital shaker at room temperature (20 to 30°C) for 24 to 48 hours to aid in the extraction of phytochemicals such as apigenin, luteolin, and quercetin. Following the extraction, the mixture is filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper to eliminate any plant residue from the methanol extract. (11).

In vitro investigation of chamomile tea extract for its phytochemical Composition

To begin the phytochemical analysis, 2-3 grams of chamomile tea extract were defatted with diethyl

ether, a non-polar solvent that efficiently eliminates lipophilic impurities such as fats, waxes, and chlorophyll. This procedure guarantees that the following extraction and analysis concentrate on polar and semi-polar phytochemicals such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins. The defatted sample was air-dried to eliminate residual solvent before proceeding with phytochemical screening. (12) (13).

Investigation of Therapeutic Potential of chamomile tea extract in management of insulin resistance in obese female patients

Selection of Subjects

A total of sixty obese female participants, aged between 45 and 55 years and presenting with a (BMI) more than 30 kg/m², were recruited for this study following the acquisition of informed consent. To guarantee variety and decrease selection bias, these people were drawn from several hospitals' outpatient departments using a randomized sample approach. All individuals were confirmed to be free of any continuing pharmaceutical treatment for obesity at the time of enrolment, reducing confounding variables related to drug effects. The inclusion criteria were closely followed in order to preserve the research population's integrity and ensure that the observed outcomes were due to the intervention under consideration rather than external therapeutic factors. This recruitment technique is consistent with ethical research guidelines and supports the validity of the study's findings.

Table I: Selection Criteria

Exclusion Criteria	Inclusion criteria
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Female patients with comorbid conditions such as diabetes or ischemic heart disease. 2. Women who were pregnant, planning to become pregnant, or currently lactating. 3. Females undergoing any form of medication or treatment specifically for obesity. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Female patients with aged between 45 and 55 2. Female years of age presenting with a body mass index (BMI) above 30 kg/m²

Study period and Duration

The study was conducted for period of 45 days, on the basis of a controlled randomized trial (13)

Treatment Groups and Plan

The study population, which included sixty obese female volunteers aged 45-55 years, was randomly assigned to three equal groups of twenty patients each to assess the effects of chamomile tea extract on obesity-related indicators. Group I acted as the control group and received no intervention during the research period, establishing a baseline for comparative analysis. In contrast, Group II and Group III were chosen as treatment groups, and they received standardized amounts of chamomile tea leaf

extract. Group II was given a daily dose of 300 mg of extract on capsules whilst Group III received a greater dose of 600 mg respectively. Both treatment groups consumed the extract once daily, precisely 30 minutes after breakfast, to ensure consistency in absorption and minimize variability due to dietary influences. The encapsulated form of the extract was chosen to enhance bioavailability and facilitate accurate dosing. This intervention protocol was maintained consistently across the study duration to assess the dose-dependent effects of chamomile tea extract on metabolic outcomes in obese individuals.

Table II: Experimental Study Design

Treatment Groups	Title	Treatment
T ₀	placebo	Without Treatment
T ₁	Treatment group-I	300mg of extract
T ₂	Treatment group II	600mg of chamomile tea extract

Serum blood Collection and analyses

In this investigation, blood samples were collected from each subject antecubital vein with sterile, single-use syringes and vacutainer tubes. To assure sample integrity and participant safety, skilled phlebotomists drew 5 cubic centimeters (cc) under aseptic circumstances. The obtained blood was immediately transferred to EDTA-coated tubes to prevent coagulation and preserve plasma components. Plasma was separated from samples by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. It was then aliquoted and refrigerated at -20°C for biochemical analysis. To evaluate **insulin resistance**, plasma insulin concentrations were measured using a **commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit**, following the manufacturer's protocol. The ELISA technique is widely recognized for its sensitivity and specificity in detecting hormone levels, including insulin, in biological fluids. TAC and TOS were also observed in the patients after the ending of

trial to check oxidative stress in the body This method aligns with established protocols in clinical biochemistry and epidemiological studies, ensuring reproducibility and accuracy in assessing metabolic health.(14) (15) (16).

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted using the two-sample t-test in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) to determine significance ($p < 0.05$). The results were presented as mean \pm SD. All statistical results were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 20.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study was designed to assess the phytochemical content of chamomile tea extract and its potential therapeutic benefits on key metabolic indicators. The study specifically aimed to investigate changes in glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), total antioxidant capacity and total oxidative stress in treatment groups

after chamomile tea administration. To examine the extract's effect on glycemic control and oxidative balance, measurements were taken at baseline (Day 0) and 45 days into the intervention period. This methodology allows for a comparison examination of pre- and post-treatment results, revealing the impact of chamomile tea in regulating metabolic health indices.

Phytochemical Characterization of Chamomile Tea leaves Extract

The chamomile tea leaf extract was quantitatively analyzed using standard spectrophotometric methods to measure its total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC). The extract contained a significant amount of bioactive phytochemicals, as shown in Table II. These compounds were quantified and expressed in milligrams of Gallic acid equivalents (mg GAE) per grams of sample, which is a commonly used metric for determining phenolic content in plant-based materials. The presence of these phytochemicals highlights the therapeutic value.

Table III: Phytochemical profile of Chamomile tea Extract

Content	Amount mg Gallic acid gram (mgGAE/g)
Total Phenolic content (TPC)	252.4±6.19
Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)	4.42±10.02

Investigation of therapeutic effects of chamomile tea Extract in management of insulin resistance and oxidase stress parameters

The purpose of this study was to look into the therapeutic effect of chamomile tea extract on obese female participants. Participants in the control group (T₀) received no therapy, whereas participants in treatment groups I (T₁) and II (T₂) received

encapsulated chamomile leaved extract at doses of 300 mg and 600 mg once a day, respectively, for 45 days.

Oxidative Stress parameters

Results showed that due to consumption of chamomile tea the obese patients has significant reduction in oxidative stress parameters in their blood and increase in antioxidant capacity as compared to normal control.

Table IV. Antioxidant analyses of chamomile tea extract (mmolTrolox)

Duration at 60 th day	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	p-value
TAC mmolTrolox	5.2234	6.95667	8.8552	p<0.05
TOS mmolTrolox	18898	78898	41682	p<0.05

HbA1c Levels of Female obese patients

The experiment indicated a significant (p<0.05) decrease in HbA1c levels in blood in both experimental groups in response to chamomile tea extract. Both experimental group showed a reduction

in HbA1c, indicating a favourable concern in managing insulin resistance. However, the control group had higher random blood sugar levels on the 45th day compared to the 0th day.

Table V. Mean±S.D for HbA1c Level of Female Subjects

Duration	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	p-value
0 day	9.89±2.10	10.03±0.31	10.97±1.32	p<0.05
60 th day	8.97±1.43	8.52±0.50	6.91±1.16	p<0.05

T₀ = No Treatment, T₁=300 mg of chamomile tea leaves extract, T₂= 600mg chamomile tea extracts extract.

DISCUSSIONS

In this study, chamomile tea extract was tested for its ability to reduce insulin resistance and oxidative stress in obese female individuals. The findings add to the expanding body of information demonstrating that chamomile has considerable pharmacological capabilities, owing to its high flavonoid and terpene concentration. These chemicals are renowned for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-diabetic properties.(17).Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) has been extensively researched for its therapeutic properties. According to a comprehensive review by Sah et al. (2022), chamomiles has high antioxidant action by trapping free radicals ions and decrease the oxidative stress in blood, which is a major contributor to insulin resistance and metabolic diseases. Furthermore, another clinical investigation including persons with type 2 diabetes found that frequent use of chamomile tea dramatically reduced inflammatory markers and improved glycemic control, reinforcing its function in regulating insulin resistance. (18) Chamomile extract in the current study most likely increased its bioavailability and stability, allowing for more effective delivery of its active ingredients. This formulation strategy could have contributed to the observed improvements in metabolic markers in obese female individuals. These findings highlight chamomile's therapeutic potential as a supplementary intervention for metabolic disorders, particularly in people at risk for type 2 diabetes. Future research should focus on the long-term benefits of encapsulated chamomile extract.

and its potential synergistic interactions with other phytochemicals, such as those found in chamomile tea.(19). One study found that encapsulated chamomile tea extract effectively reduced HbA1c levels, a critical indicator of long-term glycemic management, in obese female individuals. This shows that chamomile may boost insulin sensitivity and minimize persistent hyperglycemia, most likely through the control of oxidative stress pathways.(20).A comprehensive review published on

Clinician.com emphasized chamomile's function in improving glycemic management and lowering oxidative stress. According to the review, chamomile's polyphenol composition, which includes apigenin and luteolin, helps it scavenge free radicals and modulate inflammatory reactions. (21) .Another study that looked at the effect of chamomile polyphenols in obese rats on inflammatory cytokines and oxidative stress-induced damage found that chamomile tea polyphenols reduced the release of inflammatory cytokines in obese female rats as well as the production of reactive oxygen species in their bodies. A study also found that chamomile tea prevents muscle damage caused by oxidative stress in obese female rats (22).A study found that chamomile tea extract helped to reduce insulin resistance in obese female individuals. Another study investigated the role of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), a strong catechin prevalent in chamomile tea extract and occasionally included in chamomile formulations. This study discovered that EGCG dramatically decreased oxidative stress indicators in diabetic animals and suggested that nanoparticle formulations of EGCG could improve its bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy. These findings suggest a promising avenue for combining chamomile extract with EGCG-based Nano therapies to target oxidative stress more effectively. The integration of EGCG into chamomile-based treatments could amplify the antioxidant effects, offering a synergistic approach to managing diabetes-related complications. Moreover, encapsulation techniques not only protect the phytochemicals from degradation but also improve their absorption, making them more effective in clinical applications.

CONCLUSION

Chamomile tea extract showed significant therapeutic properties in management of insulin resistance and oxidative stress due to its rich phenolic composition. The presence of phenolic compounds enhances its antioxidant capacity, helping to neutralize free

radicals and reduce inflammation. These bioactive compounds contribute to improved glycemic control, as evidenced by reductions in HbA1c levels. Encapsulation further boosts the extract's bioavailability, making it more effective in clinical applications. Overall, chamomile tea extract offers a promising natural intervention for metabolic disorders, especially when formulated to preserve its phytochemical integrity

Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest among the authors of the study.

Acknowledgement

Efforts of all authors are highly acknowledged for this study.

REFERENCES

- Reaven, G.M., 1995. Pathophysiology of insulin resistance in human disease. *Physiological reviews*, 75(3), pp.473-486.
- Goldstein, B.J., Ahmad, F., Ding, W., Li, P.M. and Zhang, W.R., 1998. Regulation of the insulin signalling pathway by cellular protein-tyrosine phosphatases. *Molecular and cellular biochemistry*, 182(1), pp.91-99.
- Ota, T., 2014. Obesity-induced inflammation and insulin resistance. *Frontiers in endocrinology*, 5, p.204.
- Ota, T., 2014. Obesity-induced inflammation and insulin resistance. *Frontiers in endocrinology*, 5, p.204.
- Ginsberg, H.N., 2000. Insulin resistance and cardiovascular disease. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 106(4), pp.453-458.
- Singh, O., Khanam, Z., Misra, N. and Srivastava, M.K., 2011. Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.): an overview. *Pharmacognosy reviews*, 5(9), p.82
- Bayliak, M.M., Dmytriv, T.R., Melnychuk, A.V., Strilets, N.V., Storey, K.B. and Lushchak, V.I., 2021. Chamomile as a potential remedy for obesity and metabolic syndrome. *EXCLI journal*, 20, p.1261.
- Azmir, J., Zaidul, I.S.M., Rahman, M.M., Sharif, K.M., Mohamed, A., Sahena, F., Jahurul, M.H.A., Ghafoor, K., Norulaini, N.A. and Omar, A.K., 2013. Techniques for extraction of bioactive compounds from plant materials: A review. *Journal of food engineering*, 117(4), pp.426-436.
- Srivastava, J.K., Shankar, E. and Gupta, S., 2010. Chamomile: A herbal medicine of the past with a bright future. *Molecular medicine reports*, 3(6), pp.895-901.
- Harborne, A.J., 1998. *Phytochemical methods a guide to modern techniques of plant analysis*. springer science & business media.
- Anyanele, W.C., Anyanele, S.I. and Ejidike, C.S., 2022. Comparative study on the phytochemical analysis of the leaves and stem of *Ageratum houstonianum* Mill. *Asian Plant Research Journal*, 9(2), pp.49-55.
- Bhide, A., Shah, P.S. and Acharya, G., 2018. A simplified guide to randomized controlled trials. *Acta obstetrica et gynecologica Scandinavica*, 97(4), pp.380-387.
- Park, K., Gross, M., Lee, D.H., Holvoet, P., Himes, J.H., Shikany, J.M. and Jacobs Jr, D.R., 2009. Oxidative stress and insulin resistance: the coronary artery risk development in young adults study. *Diabetes care*, 32(7), pp.1302-1307.
- Piya, M.K., Harte, A.L., Sivakumar, K., Tripathi, G., Voyias, P.D., James, S., Sabico, S., Al-Daghri, N.M., Saravanan, P., Barber, T.M. and Kumar, S., 2014. The identification of irisin in human cerebrospinal fluid: influence of adiposity, metabolic markers, and gestational diabetes. *American Journal of Physiology*

- Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 306(5), pp.E512-E518.
- Ye, D., Wu, C., Cai, L., Howatt, D.A., Liang, C.L., Katsumata, Y., Mullick, A.E., Temel, R.E., Danser, A.J., Daugherty, A. and Lu, H.S., 2023. Antisense oligonucleotides targeting hepatic angiotensinogen reduce atherosclerosis and liver steatosis in hypercholesterolemic mice. *Global translational medicine*, 2(1), p.288.
- McKay, D.L. and Blumberg, J.B., 2006. A review of the bioactivity and potential health benefits of chamomile tea (*Matricaria recutita* L.). *Phytotherapy Research: An International Journal Devoted to Pharmacological and Toxicological Evaluation of Natural Product Derivatives*, 20(7), pp.519-530.
- moghaddasi Mohammad, S., 2011. Study on Camomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) usage and Farming. *Advances in Environmental Biology*, pp.1446-1454.
- Pino, J.A., Bayat, F., Marbot, R. and Agüero, J., 2002. Essential oil of chamomile *Chamomilla recutita* (L.) Rausch. from Iran. *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 14(6), pp.407-408.
- Haghi, G., Hatami, A., Safaei, A. and Mehran, M., 2014. Analysis of phenolic compounds in *Matricaria chamomilla* and its extracts by UPLC-UV. *Research in pharmaceutical sciences*, 9(1), pp.31-37.
- Srivastava, J.K. and Gupta, S., 2007. Antiproliferative and apoptotic effects of chamomile extract in various human cancer cells. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 55(23), pp.9470-9478.
- Bayliak, M.M., Dmytriv, T.R., Melnychuk, A.V., Strilets, N.V., Storey, K.B. and Lushchak, V.I., 2021. Chamomile as a potential remedy for obesity and metabolic syndrome. *EXCLI journal*, 20, p.1261.
1. Khalesi, Z.B., Beiranvand, S.P. and Bokaie, M., 2019. Efficacy of chamomile in the treatment of premenstrual syndrome: a systematic review. *Journal of pharmacopuncture*, 22(4), p.204